

BUILD SMART SEARCH INTERFACES: USE PROMPTS TO TURN QUESTIONS INTO SOLR QUERIES WITH MINIMAL CODING

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Abstract – This 1.5-hour tutorial will present a basic workflow for integrating LLM APIs into the document search systems for digital preservation, curation and discovery applications with LLM prompts and minimal coding. Participants will learn to implement a web interface that transforms users’ natural language questions into structured Solr queries to retrieve relevant documents. The tutorial will be divided into three main sections: Prompt-based web app implementation with Typescript and LLM API integration (60 minutes), followed by web interface optimization strategies to manage API latency (20 minutes). The last 10 minutes will conclude with a discussion of ethical considerations, limitations, and future directions for AI within digital preservation contexts. Participants will leave with practical code samples, implementation strategies, and a deeper understanding of how LLM integration can enhance discovery and access in digital collections.

Submission Type – Tutorial

Keywords – AI, LLM, Web Interface Development, User Experience, Document Search

Conference Topics –Tütaki – Encounter

I. INTRODUCTION

This 1.5-hour tutorial will introduce knowledge to integrate LLM-powered APIs into existing document search web applications. As the representatives of modern artificial intelligence capabilities, Large Language Models (LLMs) have become the flagships of advanced AI companies, such as ChatGPT for OpenAI [1], Grok for xAI [2], and Gemini for Google [3].

Digital preservation professionals routinely work with vast document collections that require sophisticated search capabilities. Traditional keyword-based search systems often need complex add-ons to accommodate semantic understanding and contextual relevance, creating gaps between user intent and search results. By leveraging LLM APIs as an intelligent intermediary layer, users can interact with document repositories with human languages, enabling natural language queries that are automatically translated into precise search parameters.

II. TARGET AUDIENCE

This tutorial is designed for:

- 1) Digital library application developers and designers who are new to LLM integrations and seeking to integrate these capabilities into systems.
- 2) Digital preservation specialists and systems librarians interested in revolutionizing users’ search experience but lacking extensive web interface development experience.

III. CONTENT OUTLINE

A. *Connect LLM API to Change the Search Experience* – 60 minutes

- 1) (*Knowledge Presentation*) *Introduction* - 30 minutes: The presentation will start with a concise history of AI and LLMs, transitioning to an analysis of

the current LLM ecosystem. The presenter then will compare commercial versus open-source LLM APIs, followed by a demonstration contrasting traditional keyword-based search methodologies with LLM-powered question-answering interfaces. The session will conclude with a balanced evaluation of the pros and cons of both approaches.

2) *(Hands-on) Build the Basic LLM-API Integrated Web App - 30 minutes*: This section will teach participants the integration of LLM API into web applications via a hands-on project. The presenter will briefly introduce TypeScript, LLM API and Next.js with corresponding LLM prompts first, then ask the participants to access a collaborative coding environment where they'll explore the project structure, complete key implementation components including LLM API integration and prompt engineering and ultimately test their functioning application locally.

B. *(Hands-on) Optimize the Latency in Web Interface – 20 minutes*

Expanding on the previous session's implementation of traditional loading patterns for managing LLM API latency, this session will introduce five advanced web interface loading strategies that provide users with meaningful engagement during response generation. Participants will enhance the existing project by trying these patterns via LLM prompts to generate the required code. The session will conclude with an analysis of optimal use cases for each loading strategy.

C. *(Discussion) Conclusion – 10 minutes*

The presenter will summarize the tutorial's key learning outcomes, followed by presenting thought-provoking questions for participants to share with colleagues after the conference. These questions will explore how LLM APIs might transform the digital preservation industry, potential innovations in traditional preservation technologies and user experiences, and the likely workforce impacts.

IV. MATERIALS AND RESOURCES

The presenter will prepare a collaborative codebase for participants to use during the hands-on sessions. A draft example application is shown in Fig. 1 (for section B), though this may be modified if the proposal is accepted [4]:

Fig. 1. Drafted Hands-on Project for Session B

V. CONCLUSION AND EXPECTED IMPACT

This tutorial will bridge the LLM to the traditional document search journey by guiding participants through the implementation of an LLM-enhanced search interface using the LLM API and Next.js with a basic Solr-powered document base. The tutorial will address not only the technical implementation but also critical web interface design patterns to manage the inherent latency challenges that arise when incorporating AI services into interactive digital search applications. Participants will gain the skills to deploy these technologies within their own institutional contexts.

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Pengyin Shan is a senior research software engineer at the National Center for Supercomputing Applications at the University of Illinois. She possesses extensive library application and full-stack development experience for universities across the US and Canada and has worked on several projects integrating LLM into data discovery systems.

